

8-Theory - $E = MC^2$

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Abstract:

By analyzing the 8T framework of varying curvature, and in particular the idea of mass to be converging curvature, it is possible to explain the famous equation of Einstein in a new way. The equation describes a curvature converged to a point transforming into curvature diverging on the metric tensor. Similar to enticing a spring, which is curvature on the metric tensor. Analysis will use the quark masses equation and the primorial coupling constant equation.

Introduction

We have seen that there is an almost perfect decreasing series of masses, associated with $8 - (1)$ variations, as given by equations (1) and (1.1), the versions differ by a factor of nine.

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9}; \quad (1)$$

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_E = 2E ; E \geq 1$$

That is in contrast to bosonic propagations associated with the coupling series, starting with $8 + (1)$ as given by equations (1.2) to (1.5)

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.3)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.4)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.5)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) \dots$$

Einstein equation between mass and energy is than can be explained in the following fashion. The transformation between converging curvature on the matrix tensor, to diverging curvature, a ripple across the matrix tensor. That ripple is bosonic in nature, as it involves the speed of light and it propagates all across similar to a bosonic wave of the form $2N_1 + 1$ in spin representation of the coupling constants series as given by equations (1.6) to (1.8).

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \quad (1.6)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \quad (1.7)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1 \quad (1.8)$$

Einstein idea is than expressing a certain morphism between converging curvature to diverging curvature, and also from the new framework we can simplify the idea of Energy. Energy is a measure of curvature on the matrix tensor. Energy is converging is mass, energy is diverging is synonymous to the coupling constants. Energy is absorbed and emitted in discrete amounts, isomorphic to primes or one for the coupling constant series.

In contrast to Einstein theory, our definition of energy is inclusive of particle masses and of Bosons. We have proven Bosons to be net curvature on the manifold. So bosons according to our definition is diverging energy on the matrix tensor, in agreement with the phenomena of photon pressure for example. The reversed process is of course possible, it is possible to combine diverging energies toward a morphism of mass. We can represent Einstein idea in a new way, maybe not calculative but calculation is not the point in the 8T as it almost merely mathematical. We can parametrized the patterns of converging and diverging curvatures

$$8 - (1) \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_c$$

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_d$$

Curvature diverging \mathcal{G}_d is equal to curvature converging, \mathcal{G}_c , times the square of speed of light. A new version of the Einstein equation, equation (1.9).

$$\mathcal{G}_d = \mathcal{G}_c c^2 \quad (1.9)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Coupling constants series, Spin Symmetries and Unbounded electrons" In: (2021)
- [1] O. Manor. "8T Curvature Spikes" In: (2021)